

You Were Always on My Mind: Introducing Chef's Hat and COPPER for Personalized Reinforcement Learning

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Reinforcement learning simulation environments pose an important experimental testbed and
4 facilitate data collection for developing AI-based robot applications. Most of them, however, focus
5 on single-agent tasks, which limits their application to the development of social agents. This paper
6 proposes the Chef's Hat Simulation environment, which implements a multi-agent competitive
7 card game that is a complete reproduction of the homonymous board game designed to provoke
8 competitive strategies in humans as well as emotional responses. The game showed to be ideal
9 for developing personalized reinforcement learning, in an online learning closed-loop scenario,
10 as its state representation is extremely dynamic and directly related to each of the opponent's
11 actions. To adapt current reinforcement learning agents to this scenario, we also developed
12 the COMpetitive Prioritized Experience Replay (COPPER) algorithm. With the help of Copper
13 and Chef's Hat Simulation environment, we evaluated: (1) 12 experimental learning agents,
14 trained via 4 different regimens (self-play, play against a naive baseline, PER, or COPPER) with
15 3 algorithms based on different state of the art learning paradigms (PPO, DQN, and ACER), and
16 two "dummy" baseline agents that take random actions. (2) the performance difference between
17 COPPER and PER agents trained using the PPO algorithm, and playing against different agents
18 (PPO, DQN, ACER) or all DQN agents, and (3) human performance when playing against two
19 different collections of agents. Our experiments demonstrate that COPPER helps agents learn to
20 adapt towards different types of opponents, improving the performance when compared to offline
21 learning models. An additional contribution of the paper is the formalization of the Chef's Hat
22 competitive game and the implementation of the Chef's Hat Player club, a collection of trained
23 and assessed agents as an enabler for embedding human competitive strategies in social-based
24 continual and competitive reinforcement learning.

25 **Keywords:** Continual Reinforcement Learning, Human Modelling Through Online Games, Opponent-aware Competitive Learning,
26 Simulation Environment for Reinforcement Learning

1 INTRODUCTION

27 Modeling competitive and cooperative behavior as a continual adaptation mechanism is one of the most
28 important, and challenging goals of human-robot interaction (Crossman et al., 2018). The tasks that social
29 robots are expected to perform in the near future demand not only effective perception of social cues,

30 but also the understanding of intentions and contextual interactions , along with human-like decision-
31 making. In particular, the development of cognitive architectures to deal with social interactions became of
32 great interest in recent years (Franklin et al., 2013; Sandini et al., 2018; Tanevska et al., 2020; Gorbunov
33 et al., 2019). Social interactions are highly complex, and to allow fluent and natural cooperation with
34 humans, artificial agents must take into consideration the continual and dynamic aspects of human social
35 behavior. Providing the proper response, which sometimes needs to be what the partner expects and
36 sometimes needs to be novel and interesting, is one of the most important measures to achieve a natural
37 engagement with an artificial agent (Hirokawa et al., 2018).

38 A common problem, however, arises when developing social agents behaviors resembling the richness
39 of human interaction and decision making. To design, evaluate, and validate such systems in a life-long
40 learning scenario is an expensive task, even in closed-loop scenarios, since many examples from different
41 persons, behaving in different manners and situations are needed. This usually makes such scenarios not
42 reproducible, or challenging to evaluate in long-term performance. Due to this limitation, most of the
43 current solutions for social cognitive architectures in robots are based on interaction strategies focused
44 on one-time simple decision-making (Van de Perre et al., 2018), or rely upon simple decision trees for
45 generating somehow expected behaviors based on a single-task observation space (Tuyen et al., 2018).

46 Games are shown to be a useful tool to restrict the number and type of interactions, while still providing
47 a richness of interaction possibilities more similar to that encountered in the real-world. To address the
48 problem of providing a standard and easily reproducible online interaction scenario for the development of
49 artificial social agents, we developed and validated a novel card game (Barros et al., 2020a). The game,
50 named Chef's Hat, was designed to be played by four subjects and contains a complex strategy formation
51 that is directly affected by how the opponents play the game. The entire game-flow was designed to be
52 easily adapted to artificial agents, without breaking the natural interaction observed when humans play it.

53 In a recent investigation (Barros et al., 2020b), we demonstrated that learning agents can play the game
54 and present a good performance, measured as number of victories, when playing against each other. We
55 observed that each agent learned a different gameplay style, based on the learning algorithm each of them
56 implements. All the evaluated agents, however, learn in an offline manner, which reduces their applicability
57 in a real-world scenario and replicates what has been shown in most of the recently proposed simulation
58 environments.

59 In this paper, we extend and formalize the online learning version of the Chef's Hat simulation
60 environment. To validate it, we introduce COMpetitive Prioritized Experience Replay (COPPER), to
61 provide reinforcement learning agents the ability to learn and adapt towards other opponents continuously.
62 COPPER implements another weight on the prioritized experience replay algorithm, relating specific
63 experiences with specific opponents. [Moreover, the COPPER is a continual learning algorithm \(Kheparthal et al. 2021\) algorithm but can be distinguished as a form of 'personalized' learning.](#)

65 Our experiments aim to demonstrate how our online learning agents compare with the existing off-line
66 Chef's Hat players (Barros et al., 2020b) and, in a smaller scale with human players, by using an extension
67 of the environment that allows humans to play against the trained agents. We extend three agents, based
68 on Deep Q-Learning (DQL) (Mnih et al., 2013), Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) (Schulman et al.,
69 2017), Actor-Critic with Experience Replay (ACER) (Wang et al., 2016), to learn online how to play the
70 game. We implement in total 12 versions of offline and online agents to better explain the contribution
71 of COPPER on competitive reinforcement learning. This way, we made these agents create personalized
72 strategies to beat their opponents.

73 Our entire evaluation is based on a tournament scenario where all the developed agents play several
74 rounds of Chef's Hat against each other. In our analysis, we evaluate the behavior of the agents, in terms of
75 the number of victories and track the performance over the number of played games. We discuss how the
76 online learning agents can adapt and develop a fast-paced strategy learning behavior when playing against
77 the offline learning agents. We also analyse the role of COPPER in adapting faster towards an opponent's
78 strategy. Finally, in our small-scaled human experiment, we are able to discuss how there is a trend that
79 demonstrates that the performance of the online learning agents is better when playing against humans
80 when compared with the offline trained agents.

81 As a contribution of this paper, first we introduce the formalization of a reproducible and challenging
82 simulation scenario for multiple agents. Second, we provide the Chef's Hat Players Club as a collection

83 of implemented, ready-to-use, and evaluated agents for Chef's Hat with the hope to facilitate future
84 development of this environment and, moreover, to facilitate the advancement of the research on online and
85 personalized competitive learning in social contexts. Third, we propose the novel COMpetitive Prioritized
86 Experience Replay (COPPER) algorithm and analyze it in a competitive multi-player continual learning
87 scenario, showing its advantages in comparison to the Prioritized Experience Replay (PER) algorithm.

2 RELATED WORK

88 The limitation on designing, implementing, and evaluating realistic interaction scenarios, in particular
89 where multiple people are involved and perform a lasting interaction, is one of the problems that must be
90 solved before the deployment of artificial agents, such as robots, in real life. Robots do not have universal
91 skills yet, so most of the common interaction scenarios provide a restricted action space. To overcome
92 this limitation, several human-robot and human-agent-based scenarios are developed as games, as they
93 have been proven to capture some relevant aspects of natural group interaction. For instance, a game
94 specially designed to favor one and disfavor another player in a multiplayer interaction was shown to
95 provoke emotional reactions (Barakova et al., 2015), which lasted during the repetitive games between the
96 same players (Gorbunov et al., 2017).

97 With the recent development of reinforcement learning algorithms, the design and implementation of
98 adaptable simulation environments flourished (Brockman et al., 2016). Such environments allow fast-paced
99 simulations of different tasks, the calculation of specific step-reward functions and are the basis for the
100 recent groundbreaking applications of deep reinforcement learning. Most of these scenarios, however, are
101 not developed to be used in continual or online learning tasks, nor on social interactions, as they usually
102 focus on optimizing one single task. Most of them simulate situations that are based on single agents (Shi
103 et al., 2019), classic reinforcement learning problems (Cullen et al., 2018), robotic simulations (Zamora
104 et al., 2016), or, more recently, playing video games (Torrado et al., 2018).

105 Although there is a recent interest in continual and online reinforcement learning (Lomonaco et al., 2020),
106 most of these applications and scenarios take into consideration single-agents or non-social interactions
107 Khetarpal et al. (2020). The development of online reinforcement learning towards social applications, in
108 particular competitive environments, is still to be largely explored, although there exists a relevant effort on
109 multi-agent investigation Nekoei et al. (2021). The focus on generalization makes these solutions ideal
110 for multi-task learning but hinders them from developing personalized strategies when facing multiple
111 opponents in a competitive game, for example.

112 To evaluate online and competitive reinforcement learning on real-world scenarios demands a strong and
113 adaptable simulation environment. Usually, this is achieved with game simulations, where the decisions of
114 an agent impact their future behavior. These environments, however, mostly focus on single-agent tasks
115 or maximum dyadic interactions. A simulation environment that relies on online learning and provides a
116 multi-agent task is still not easily available for the general public. We envision that with the formalization
117 of the Chef's Hat environment, we can fill this gap.

118 The lack of such environment, however, did not stop the study of online reinforcement learning, and
119 many researchers recently proposed different solutions for it (Lillicrap et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2018).
120 From transfer of learned representations, to constitute a life-long learning system (Abel et al., 2018), to
121 the development of a focused experience replay (Schaul et al., 2015) for tuning a policy network towards
122 adapting to new environments (Ye et al., 2020), or achieving scalable multi-task learning with several
123 workers (Zhan et al., 2017). Although these solutions seem to work well in complex tasks, most of them
124 demand a higher amount of training loops than offline Reinforcement Learning, which makes them not
125 viable in a human-artificial agent interaction scenario. Thus, in this paper, we propose a simple adaptation
126 of a prioritized experience replay, to reduce the demand of many training loops, but still leverage the
127 advantage of online learning through personalization.

3 THE CHEF'S HAT SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

128 The scenario that we propose is based on a card game played by four players. The card game scenario was
129 chosen as the underlying action-perception cycle development environment as it represents a controllable
130 situation, where each player has its turn to take specific actions, and yet provides a ground for natural
131 interaction between the players. Within this scope, we needed a game that allows the players to develop
132 strategies while playing, and that, within the game mechanics, evoked a dynamic competitive behavior.

Figure 1. Illustration of the Chef's Hat card game been played by three humans and a robot.

133 In this regard, we recently developed and validated the Chef's Hat card game (Barros et al., 2020a),
 134 illustrated in Figure 1. In this paper, we propose a 1:1 implementation of the game in an OpenAI-like
 135 Gym environment (Brockman et al., 2016). Below, we describe the game mechanics and the details of the
 136 environment functionalities.

137 **3.1 Embedded Chef's Hat Mechanics**

138 The development of the Chef's Hat mechanics followed two main principles: 1) To provide restricted,
 139 but natural, competitive interaction between the four players; 2) to provide turn-taking, i.e., an organized
 140 structure, in which an agent, has a supportive infrastructure and capacity to process incoming information
 141 and generate behavior without breaking the fluidity of the interaction.

142 The game simulates a kitchen environment, and it has a role-based hierarchy: each player can either be a
 143 Chef, a Sous-Chef, a Waiter, or a Dishwasher. The players try to be the first to get rid of their ingredient
 144 cards and become the Chef. This happens for multiple rounds (or Shifts, each of them detailed in Algorithm
 145 1) until the first player reaches 15 points.

146 As exhibited in Algorithm 1, during every Shift there are three phases: Start of the Shift, Making Pizzas,
 147 End of the Shift.

148 At the *Start of the Shift*, the cards are shuffled and dealt with by the players. Then, the exchange of roles
 149 starts based on the previous Shift end positions. Who finished first becomes the Chef, who finishes second
 150 becomes the Sous-Chef, third the Waiter, and fourth the Dishwasher. The change of roles is necessary to
 151 change the game balance, rewarding the players who finished first in the last Shift and encouraging them to
 152 win the next one. Once the roles are exchanged, the players have the chance to do a special action. If a
 153 player has two jokers at the start of the Shift in its hand, they can choose to play their special action: in the
 154 case of the Dishwasher this is *Food Fight* (the hierarchy is inverted), in case of the other roles it is *Dinner*
 155 *is served* (there will be no card exchange during the Shift). Then, unless the action "Dinner is served" is
 156 played, the exchange of the cards starts. The Dishwasher has to give the two cards with the highest values
 157 to the Chef, who in return gives back two cards of their liking. The Waiter has to give their lowest valued
 158 card to the Sous-Chef, who in return gives one card of their liking.

159 Then, the *Making of the Pizzas* starts. The person who possesses a "Golden 11" card may start making
 160 the first pizza of the Shift. A pizza is prepared when ingredient cards are played on the pizza base on
 161 the playing field. A pizza is made when no one can (or wants to) put on any ingredients anymore. The
 162 rarest cards have the lowest numbers. A card can be played if it is rarer (i.e., lower face values) than the

```

Shuffle the deck;
Deal an equal amount of cards per player;
Exchange roles;
Exchange cards;
if special action is evoked then
  | Do special action;
end
First player discard cards.
while not end of the shift do
  for each player do
    if player can, and want, to discard then
      | discard cards;
    else
      | pass;
    end
    if All players passed then
      | Clean the board;
    end
    if All players finished then
      | End of shift.
    end
  end
end

```

Algorithm 1: The playing flow of one Shift of the Chef's hat card game.

163 previously played cards. The ingredients are played from highest to the lowest number, so from 11 to
 164 1. Players can play multiple copies of an ingredient at once, but always have to play an equal or greater
 165 amount of copies than the previous player did. If a player cannot (or does not want) to play, they pass until
 166 the next pizza starts. A joker card is also available and when played together with other cards, it assumes
 167 their value. When played alone, the joker has the highest face value (12).

168 At the end of the Shift, the new roles are distributed among the players according to the order of finishing,
 169 and every player gets the number of points related to their role. The Chef gets 5 points, the Sous-Chef gets
 170 3 points, the Waiter gets 1 point and the Dishwasher gets 0 points. The game continues until one of the
 171 players reaches 15 points.

172 The ingredient cards, illustrated in Figure 2, needed to be easily recognizable by all potential players,
 173 including humans and robots, both when played on the playing field and when exchanged among players
 174 at the start of the Shift. The pictures in the cards are easy to be recognized by human players and to ease
 175 the recognition by the robots, QR-codes were added. The QR-codes allow a camera placed on top of the
 176 playing field to capture the overall game-state and save it. This is extremely important when creating a
 177 learning database to be used together with the virtual environment.

178 The cards are to be placed on the playing field, illustrated in Figure 3. To guarantee that the players lay
 179 down the cards without stacking them, and hindering them to be recognized by automatic systems, we
 180 designed the playing field to have 11 different marked places in which players could place their cards on
 181 the pizza.

182 3.2 OpenAI Gym-based Environment

183 OpenAI Gym Brockman et al. (2016) is a very popular toolkit that facilitates the development and
 184 the dissemination of simulation environments for training reinforcement learning agents. It enables the
 185 creation of standardized environments that allow the establishment of a set of specific rules for a simulation,
 186 the calculation of varied types of rewards, and the logging and visualization of training artificial agents.
 187 Recently, several simulation environments were released using the OpenAI gym, which facilitates its
 188 reproduction and evaluation with different reinforcement learning algorithms.

Figure 2. Ingredient cards, and the Joker, with their corresponding face number. The lower the number, the rarer the card.

Figure 3. Playing field where the cards are placed, representing a pizza board.

189 We ported the Chef's Hat game into the OpenAI Gym and implemented all the complex game rules
 190 and mechanics. The environment is freely available¹, and we envision that this environment will help to
 191 standardize the learning of game strategies within our card game, but also to collect and share data for
 192 different reinforcement learning-based players.

193 The environment calculates the game state by aggregating the current player's hand and the current cards
 194 on the board. Using this standard state representation we can give the learning agents the possibility to
 195 learn specific strategies purely based on the cards they hold and the cards which were displayed. Of course,
 196 as the environment is fully customizable, the current game state can be composed of any other variable
 197 which might help the agent to succeed in its task.

198 Each action taken by an agent is validated based on a lookup table, created on the fly, based on the
 199 player's hand and the cards in the current playing field, to guarantee that a taken action is allowed given
 200 the game context. The look-up-table is extremely important for games when humans are involved as it
 201 guarantees that the game rules are maintained.

202 The actions are calculated based on the number of possibilities of the lookup table. The standard game,
 203 with a deck of 121 cards, has a total of 200 possible actions, which capture all the possible moves a player
 204 can do: to discard one card of face value 1 represents one move, to discard 3 cards of face value 1 and a

¹ <https://github.com/pablovin/ChefsHatGYM>

Figure 4. Example of possible actions given a certain game state. The columns represent the card face values, and the rows represent the number of cards to be discarded. The letter "j" represents the presence of a joker. The look-up table is created on the fly, and it marks all the actions which are allowed based on the game mechanics (blue regions) and the ones which are not allowed (the gray regions). For this given game state, the player would be allowed only to perform the actions marked with the green dots.

205 joker is another move, while passing is considered as yet another move. Figure 4 illustrates an example of
 206 calculated possible actions given a game state. The blue areas mark all the possible action states, while the
 207 gray areas mark actions that are not allowed due to the game's mechanics. We observed that, given this
 208 particular game state, a player would only be allowed to perform one of three actions (marked in green),
 209 while any other action (marked in red) would be considered as invalid and not carried on.

210 The environment allows the customization of the game itself. We can easily choose how many players
 211 will be playing the game, how many cards a deck can have, and how many of the playing agents are to be

Figure 5. The Chef's Hat Online interface allows humans to play against trained agents. This solution allows the collection and exporting of the entire gameplay in a format compatible with the Chef's Hat Gym environment.

212 trained. The agents are also customized and follow a standard implementation protocol. This allows the
 213 implementation and deployment of a large variety of agents, from complex learning agents that might take
 214 external factors to learn the game strategy (e.g., from an external camera reading a real-game) to naive
 215 agents that do specific actions following simple rules.

216 For each action that an agent performs, the game environment calculates a specific reward. Again, as
 217 the environment is fully customizable, the reward calculation can be updated accordingly to the needs of
 218 the training agents. For example, giving the highest reward for an agent that performs a valid action - that
 219 means, an action that follows the game rules - can be used to train an agent to learn the rules of the game.
 220 Later on, this reward can be updated to make the agent learn how to win the game.

221 Another aspect of our environment is the logging of actions and states. It allows us to create snapshots
 222 of each played game, that can be used to create playing datasets which are extremely helpful for further
 223 training intelligent agents. Each step of the gameplay is recorded in a different set of files and can be
 224 retrieved later on with ease.

225 The stored games can be used by the environment as a modulation for specific agents to behave in a
 226 particular manner. That allows information obtained from real-world games, collected while real persons
 227 are playing it, to be easily inserted in the environment as primitives for the training of the agents. The game
 228 status of the real games can be obtained via a single camera facing the playing field, and when saved in the
 229 same format as the one used by the environment, can be imported and used during the game.

230 3.3 The Chef's Hat Online

231 In order to facilitate the integration and evaluation of the developed agents in a real-world scenario, we
 232 depict the Chef's Hat environment on the Chef's Hat Online game², illustrated in Figure 5.

233 Chef's Hat Online is a web-based interface that allows experimenters to set up a game where a human
 234 can play against three different agents. The game follows the same rules as the physical game and has
 235 an interface completely adapted for web-based interaction. It collects all the information the Gym-based
 236 environment does and saves it in the same format, allowing the use of all the logging and plotting to
 237 generate tools already present in the Gym-based environment.

² <https://github.com/pablovin/ChefsHatOnline>

4 THE CHEF'S HAT COMPETITIVE LEARNING AGENTS

238 The General Q-learning algorithm learns to maximize the probability of choosing an action that leads to
 239 maximum reward. For that, it calculates a Q-value (quality value) for each action given a state and updates
 240 the policy, in our case represented by a neural network, to maximize the expected reward. Using a temporal
 241 difference calculation, it can take into consideration a sequence of steps that leads to the final state. In our
 242 simulation environment, the final state is achieved when the player has no cards left in their hand. The
 243 maximal reward is gained, once the player is the first one to reach the final state.

4.1 Defining Chef's Hat Q-Learning

244 The typical Q-learning algorithm represents a function Q :

$$Q : S \times A \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (1)$$

246 where S is the state, in our case represented by the 28 values composed by the cards at hand and the cards
 247 at the board. The actions, A , are expressed using the 200 discrete values for all the possible actions.

248 To update the Q-values, the algorithm uses the following update function:

$$Q'(s_t, a_t) = Q(s, a) + \alpha \times (TD) \quad (2)$$

249 where t is the current step, α is a pre-defined learning rate and TD is the temporal difference function,
 250 calculated as:

$$TD = r_t \times \gamma \times \max Q(s_{t+1}, a_t) - \max Q(s_t, a_t) \quad (3)$$

251 where r_t is the obtained reward for the state (s_t) and action (a_t) association, γ represents the discount
 252 factor, a modulator that estimates the importance of the future rewards, and $\max Q(s_{t+1}, a_t)$ is the estimate
 253 of Q-value for the next state.

254 To improve the capability of Q-learning algorithms, experience replay is used to store the agent's own
 255 experience and use it to improve learning. It saves important steps taken by the agents, to increase the
 256 available data for learning state/action pairs through batch-learning.

4.2 Competitive Prioritized Experience Replay (COPPER)

258 When applied to online learning problems, Q-learning-based reinforcement learning usually presents
 259 sub-optimal results. The problem is even more critical when applied to multi-agent competitive scenarios,
 260 where an agent has to counter the opponent's actions. To achieve an optimal generalised behavior, the agent
 261 must acquire a large enough experience, which usually takes time and a high number of experiences. In the
 262 proposed scenario, the use of stored experiences biases the agents to understand that each adversary plays
 263 the game similarly to each other. In a competitive scenario, this is usually not the case.

264 Prioritized experience replay (PER) Schaul et al. (2015) can help us handle the online update aspect
 265 of competitive learning. Originally, experience replay adds a weighted probability ($P(i)$) on the recorded
 266 experienced pool, so that each experience has a different meaning when using it to update the Q-values.
 267 $P(i)$ is calculated based on the network's loss after calculating TD in a forward pass of the network (using
 268 an input i):

$$P(i) = \frac{p_a^i}{\sum_k p_a^k} \quad (4)$$

269 where a indicated how much we want to rely on the priority, p is the priority, and k the total number of
 270 saved experiences. It lacks, however, the ability to individualize the learning towards a specific opponent.
 271 So every time an agent learns using the PER, it pulls from the most successful previous experiences and
 272 iterates over them, updating its knowledge. This creates a generally good agent, but unable to adapt towards
 273 specific opponents quickly. To deal with that, we update PER by adding an individualized term.

274 As Chef's Hat is a multiplayer competitive game, our experience replay adds another information to be
 275 weighted, which is the relevance of this experience when playing against that specific opponent (o):

Name	Type	Training	Strategy
D_r	Dummy	-	Random
D_o	Dummy	-	Discard One Card
off_s	Learning	Offline	Self-play
off_n	Learning	Offline	vs Naive
on_c	Learning	Online	COPPER
on_e	Learning	Online	PER

Table 1. Structure of the Chef’s Hat Player Club containing a total of 14 different agents: 2 dummy agents and 12 learning agents, each of them implementing the listed learning strategies with DQL, PPO, ACER.

$$P(i) = o \frac{p_a^i}{\sum_k p_a^k} \quad (5)$$

276 We update o based on the relative performance of the agent in comparison with the opponents at the end
277 of each game, so if the agent was better than the opponent, these experiences have a higher impact.

5 EVALUATING ONLINE LEARNING AGENTS ON CHEF’S HAT

278 To best evaluate our COPPER-based agents, we first establish a set of opponents, as the Chef’s Hat
279 Players Club, and the tournament scenario. Each of our experiments uses agents from the Players Club and
280 investigate different aspects of COPPER-based agents.

5.1 Chef’s Hat Players Club

282 To provide a general understanding of the impact of our proposed competitive continual learning agents on
283 the Chef’s Hat environment, we introduce here the Chef’s Hat Players Club³: a collection of implemented
284 and optimized agents for Chef’s Hat.

285 First, we implement two dummy agents: one that performs random movements (D_r) and one that only
286 discards one card at a time (D_o). Then, we developed versions of agents based on Deep Q-Learning
287 (DQL) Mnih et al. (2013) (DQL), Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) Schulman et al. (2017) (PPO) and
288 Actor-Critic with Experience Replay (ACER) Wang et al. (2016) ($ACER$). These are the most popular, and
289 effective, reinforcement learning algorithms for game scenarios.

290 In our previous study (Barros et al., 2020b), we proposed two different manners to train offline these
291 agents on Chef’s Hat: make them play against the naive agents (off_n) or playing against different generations
292 of themselves in a self-play strategy (off_s). In the experiments reported in this paper we will use both
293 variations.

294 For online learning, we will implement our competitive prioritized experience replay for the three
295 agents (on_c). Also, we implement versions of them with the traditional experience replay (on_e), to better
296 understand the impact of the proposed solution.

297 In total, the Chef’s Hat Player Club is composed of 14 different agents, summarized in Table 1.

298 The Supplementary material to this paper contains a detailed explanation of how each of the agents was
299 trained and optimized to play the game. It also contains a detailed description of the final architecture of
300 each agent.

5.2 Tournament Scenario

302 To provide an experimental setup that helps us to understand better the contributions of the proposed
303 COPPER-based agents, without requiring an enormous set of combinatorial experiments, our main
304 evaluation happens in the form of a tournament among all the agents on the Chef’s Hat Players Club.

305 Each tournament is composed of two brackets of hierarchical playing phases. In each phase, the agents
306 will face each other, and the two victorious ones will advance to the next phase and play against themselves.
307 The best agents of each bracket play against each other and the victorious agent is crowned the winner of
308 the tournament.

³ <https://github.com/pablovin/ChefsHatPlayersClub>

309 To properly assess each of the types of learning agents, we implement one instance of each of them. To
310 complement the agents in order to allow the tournament to happen, we implement an equal number of
311 dummy agents until we have a total of 32 agents. In our experiments, we have 3 phases per bracket and a
312 final game to crown the champion.

313 5.3 Experimental Setup

314 Our experimental scenario serves as our ablation study, baseline, and is the bases for our discussion and
315 analyses. On it, we run 10 tournaments in a row, which allow the online learning agents to learn competitive
316 interaction. We repeat this experiment 1000 times.

317 In our analysis, first, we compute and analyze the average number of victories per agent and per
318 tournament run. This informs us of the performance of each agent, giving us the differences between offline
319 and online agents, and between the PER and COPPER-based agents.

320 Our second experiment focuses on examining the differences between COPPER and PER when playing
321 against different types of agents. We create two-game setups: one where the online learning agent plays
322 10 games in a row against three types of different agents (PPO_{offs} , DQL_{offs} and $ACER_{offs}$), and the
323 second one where the online learning agent plays 10 games in a row against the same types of agents
324 (three instances of DQL_{offs}). To simplify our analysis, and to focus on explaining the differences between
325 COPPER and PER, the online learning agents will be implemented using only one type of learning
326 algorithm, PPO_{one} and PPO_{onc} .

327 In the third experiment, humans play against the agents using the Chef's Hat Online variant of the game.
328 As playing with humans is a costly task (in terms of time and effort to organize and collect participants)
329 and since our goal is to investigate the differences between offline and online learning, and between
330 PER-based and COPPER-based agents, we simplify this experimental setup in terms of evaluated agents.
331 We asked 10 human players to play 10 games against two sets of agents: the first composed of PPO_{offs} ,
332 PPO_{offn} and D_r , and the second composed of PPO_{onc} , PPO_{one} and PPO_{offs} . The PPO implementations
333 were chosen because they are the ones with the best performance in general when compared to the other
334 two reinforcement learning algorithms. We calculate the average number of victories in each scenario. The
335 first set of experiments will help us to establish the offline benchmark, while the second one will illustrate
336 the differences between online and offline agents, in terms of performance, and between COPPER-based
337 and PER-based online learning.

6 RESULTS

338 6.1 Tournament Results

339 Our first experimental results, the average number of victories per tournament, are displayed in Figure 6,
340 together with their standard deviation. By plotting these results per agent type, we can visualize the impact
341 of online learning in each of the reinforcement learning algorithms. For all three learning agent types,
342 the DQL_{offs} variation starts with the highest average number of victories on the first games, as expected
343 based on our previous results (Barros et al., 2020b). However, after just a couple of games, the online
344 learning agents start to increase their number of victories, and in all three types of reinforcement learning
345 algorithms, overcome the offline learning strategies.

346 When compared with each other, we see that the COPPER-based agents exhibit a more steep learning
347 curve, which shows that the proposed competitive version of the prioritized experience replay enhances the
348 learning of specific strategy winning patterns when playing against different agents. Also, we see that the
349 COPPER-based agents reach a higher average number of victories, without any error overlap, showing that
350 besides a stable learning curve, they also learned more effective strategies at the end of the 10 tournaments.

351 6.2 COPPER vs PER

352 Analyzing the results of our second experiment, in Figure 7, where we create games that have PPO_{one}
353 and PPO_{onc} playing against a group of the same type and different agents, we observe the advantage of the
354 online learning methods. In all scenarios, the online learning agents present the best performance, in terms
355 of average victories, by the end of the 10 games run.

356 We can observe, also, that the COPPER achieves a higher number of victories in less games, when
357 compared with the PER agents. As COPPER has specific weights on the experience replay per type of
358 opponent, it learns how to adapt towards these specific opponents' strategies, while PER relies on a general
359 experience pool, and thus, tries to create a general, and in this case more ineffective, strategy.

Figure 6. Average number of victories (Y-axis) for 1000 runs of 10 tournaments (X-axis) in a row per agent type.

Figure 7. Average number of victories (Y-axis), in 1000 runs of 10 tournaments (X-axis), per experiment type: online learning agents vs the same types of agents, and online learning agents vs different types of agents.

360 When playing against the same type of agents, the behavior of COPPER and PER is similar, which is
 361 expected as there is no specific weight attribution to the replay pool. Thus, the agents learn using the same
 362 algorithm.

6.3 Human on the Loop

364 When playing against a human, we observe (plotted in Figure 8) that none of the agents is particularly
 365 effective. We see, however, that when playing against the online learning agents, human performance drops
 366 towards the end of the game, indicating that the online agents' performance increases. We see, also, that
 367 the COPPER-based agent achieved the best average victories when compared with the other agents.

Figure 8. Average number of victories (Y-axis), for 10 human players, per agent type when playing 10 games in a row (X-axis).

7 DISCUSSIONS

368 Our experiments demonstrate the main advantages of the COPPER algorithm and, with this, the advantages
 369 that come from using dynamic and online adaptation in multiple agents' contexts. First, COPPER improves
 370 the performance of online reinforcement learning on Chef's Hat game. Second, the proposed three
 371 experimental setups help us to quantify the degree of these improvements. However, numbers and
 372 benchmarking are not the main contributions of this paper, rather the intended contribution is summarised
 373 in the following subsections.

374 7.1 Chef's Hat Simulation Environment

375 In this paper, we describe the implementation, the evaluation and the experimental testing of a multiplayer
 376 competitive game that involves elements of reinforcement learning that are suitable for serial play instances.
 377 Also we evaluated and reported a series of complex experiments that involve standard reinforcement
 378 learning elements - a serializable state and action representation, a world representation that is easy
 379 to explain and to understand, but difficult to master, and a decision-making process that is not trivial.
 380 Moreover, differently from existing environments, we implement the Chef's Hat competitive scenario,
 381 which is designed to enable data collection related to human play strategies and therefore to facilitate the
 382 modeling of online interactions between the agents. Future development will enable the resulting model to
 383 define the playing strategies of a social robot robots.

384 Because learning the rules of a game, Chef's Hat game in particular, is not enough to generate competitive
 385 decision-making for artificial agents (Bai and Jin, 2020), learning heuristics of how the opponents play the
 386 game have a strong impact on the effectiveness of the learning agents. Allowing the agents to learn from a
 387 well-structured scenario and to adapt to continuous interactions to master how to play against other agents
 388 is one of the most significant contributions of our proposed simulation environment.

389 7.2 Chef's Hat Online

390 The web interface of the Chef's Hat simulation allows a hassle-free setup to include human-in-the-
 391 loop experiments. The capability to play the same game, using the same structure, as in the simulated
 392 environment, gives us a powerful tool to extract heuristics from human behavior and directly compare it
 393 with data from the simulation environment.

394 In our experiments, the Chef's Hat online implementation allowed us to demonstrate that our agents,
 395 although very effective when playing against each other, are still not a match for humans. The development
 396 of agents capable of playing against humans will be achieved when we start tackling the competitive aspects
 397 of Chef's Hat, in particular by understanding and modeling how humans play the game. We believe that
 398 using the Chef's Hat Online tool to evaluate different aspects of human-agent interaction will endow the
 399 development of much more complex and effective agents.

400 7.3 The Chef's Hat Players Club

401 Yet another contribution to the community of online reinforcement learning is the implementation of 12
 402 different types of learning agents for the Chef's Hat game. The Chef's Hat Players Club presents as an
 403 established collection of players, with an associated benchmark and behavioral analysis, that can serve as
 404 the basis for the future development of online reinforcement learning. Agents that are developed following
 405 the Players Club structure can take part in the Chef's Hat Simulation environment, which will facilitate the
 406 development, assessment, and reproducibility of more complex algorithms. The integration of the Player's

407 club with the Chef's Hat Online interface also allows the fast development of novel agents that leverage
408 human data.

409 **7.4 We dig COPPER, We Found Gold!**

410 COPPER is a simple, yet efficient, solution for competitive online and competitive learning based on
411 Chef's Hat. It has, however, limitations: as it is based on the experience replay, more games an agent plays,
412 the more examples are collected on the experience replay.

413 Our experiments gave us insight that COPPER will stabilize the learning of the agent at some point,
414 which makes it more robust against known opponents. If the COPPER-based agent plays against a large
415 number of players, in theory, it would be able to generalize and play against several different types of
416 opponents.

417 The main advantage of COPPER compared to the established PER algorithm is the speed at which
418 the adaptation towards specific players happens. All of our experiments demonstrated this characteristic,
419 including playing against the most complex agents of all: humans.

420 **7.5 Limitations**

421 The RL agents, especially in multiplayer setting are susceptible to large variances in performance,
422 depending on conditions. Therefore, although COPPER has a faster adaptation when compared to the PER
423 agent on the scenario with different opponents and COPPER-base agent achieved the best average victories
424 when compared to the other agents in our experiments, performance variance is not considered and more
425 data-gathering and statistical validation will be needed in the future.

8 CONCLUSIONS

426 In this paper, we introduce COPPER, a competitive experience replay algorithm for online reinforcement
427 learning. To be able to better explain, assess and provide our solution to the research community, we also
428 propose a series of tools: a novel simulation environment, that implements the a card game (the Chef's
429 Hat) in a 1:1 manner; the Chef's Hat Online interface, that allows assessment and data collection from
430 agents playing against humans; and the Chef's Hat Player club, a collection of implemented, trained and
431 benchmarked agents on the Chef's Hat game.

432 Chef's Hat showed to be a plausible candidate for multi-agent and dynamic competitive interactions. We
433 run an extensive number of experiments and demonstrate that our COPPER-based agents learn faster and
434 more effectively than offline and experience replay-based online agents.

435 *Although the holistic analysis of COPPER demonstrates that its simple architecture learns how to adapt
436 to different opponents playing Chef's Hat over time, it still relies on several collected samples. We believe
437 that investigating different opponent prediction mechanisms could help even further in the development of
438 next-level competitive learning agents. In this paper, we scratched the surface of an investigation of the
439 behavior and performance of the COPPER-based agents against human players. Exploring this side of the
440 work, and, understanding the modeling of dynamic strategies from humans, is important future work.*

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REFERENCES

- 443 Abel, D., Arumugam, D., Lehnert, L., and Littman, M. (2018). State abstractions for lifelong reinforcement
444 learning. In *International Conference on Machine Learning* (PMLR), 10–19
- 445 Bai, Y. and Jin, C. (2020). Provable self-play algorithms for competitive reinforcement learning. In
446 *International Conference on Machine Learning* (PMLR), 551–560
- 447 Barakova, E. I., Gorbunov, R., and Rauterberg, M. (2015). Automatic interpretation of affective facial
448 expressions in the context of interpersonal interaction. *IEEE transactions on human-machine systems*
449 45, 409–418
- 450 [Dataset] Barros, P., Sciutti, A., Hootsmans, I. M., Opheij, L. M., Toebosch, R. H. A., and Barakova, E.
451 (2020a). It's food fight! introducing the chef's hat card game for affective-aware hri
- 452 Barros, P., Tanevska, A., and Sciutti, A. (2020b). Learning from learners: Adapting reinforcement learning
453 agents to be competitive in a card game. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.04000*

- 454 Brockman, G., Cheung, V., Pettersson, L., Schneider, J., Schulman, J., Tang, J., et al. (2016). Openai gym.
455 *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.01540*
- 456 Crossman, M. K., Kazdin, A. E., and Kitt, E. R. (2018). The influence of a socially assistive robot on
457 mood, anxiety, and arousal in children. *Professional Psychology: Research and Practice* 49, 48
- 458 Cullen, M., Davey, B., Friston, K. J., and Moran, R. J. (2018). Active inference in openai gym: A paradigm
459 for computational investigations into psychiatric illness. *Biological psychiatry: cognitive neuroscience*
460 *and neuroimaging* 3, 809–818
- 461 Franklin, S., Madl, T., D' mello, S., and Snaider, J. (2013). Lida: A systems-level architecture for cognition,
462 emotion, and learning. *IEEE Transactions on Autonomous Mental Development* 6, 19–41
- 463 Gorbunov, R., Barakova, E. I., and Rauterberg, M. (2017). Memory effect in expressed emotions during
464 long term group interactions. In *International Work-Conference on the Interplay Between Natural and*
465 *Artificial Computation* (Springer), 254–264
- 466 Gorbunov, R. D., Rauterberg, M., and Barakova, E. I. (2019). A cognitive model of social preferences in
467 group interactions. *Integrated Computer-Aided Engineering* 26, 185–196
- 468 Hirokawa, M., Funahashi, A., Itoh, Y., and Suzuki, K. (2018). Adaptive behavior acquisition of a
469 robot based on affective feedback and improvised teleoperation. *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive and*
470 *Developmental Systems*
- 471 Khetarpal, K., Riemer, M., Rish, I., and Precup, D. (2020). Towards continual reinforcement learning: A
472 review and perspectives. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2012.13490*
- 473 Lillicrap, T. P., Hunt, J. J., Pritzel, A., Heess, N., Erez, T., Tassa, Y., et al. (2015). Continuous control with
474 deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1509.02971*
- 475 Lomonaco, V., Desai, K., Culurciello, E., and Maltoni, D. (2020). Continual reinforcement learning in 3d
476 non-stationary environments. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and*
477 *Pattern Recognition Workshops*. 248–249
- 478 Mnih, V., Kavukcuoglu, K., Silver, D., Graves, A., Antonoglou, I., Wierstra, D., et al. (2013). Playing atari
479 with deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.5602*
- 480 Nekoei, H., Badrinaaraayanan, A., Courville, A., and Chandar, S. (2021). Continuous coordination as a
481 realistic scenario for lifelong learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2103.03216*
- 482 Sandini, G., Mohan, V., Sciutti, A., and Morasso, P. (2018). Social cognition for human-robot
483 symbiosis—challenges and building blocks. *Frontiers in neurorobotics* 12, 34
- 484 Schaul, T., Quan, J., Antonoglou, I., and Silver, D. (2015). Prioritized experience replay. *arXiv preprint*
485 *arXiv:1511.05952*
- 486 Schulman, J., Wolski, F., Dhariwal, P., Radford, A., and Klimov, O. (2017). Proximal policy optimization
487 algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1707.06347*
- 488 Shi, B., Ozsoy, M. G., Hurley, N., Smyth, B., Tragos, E. Z., Geraci, J., et al. (2019). Pyrecgym: a
489 reinforcement learning gym for recommender systems. In *Proceedings of the 13th ACM Conference on*
490 *Recommender Systems*. 491–495
- 491 Tanevska, A., Rea, F., Sandini, G., Cañamero, L., and Sciutti, A. (2020). A socially adaptable framework
492 for human-robot interaction. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI* 7, 121. doi:10.3389/frobt.2020.00121
- 493 Torrado, R. R., Bontrager, P., Togelius, J., Liu, J., and Perez-Liebana, D. (2018). Deep reinforcement
494 learning for general video game ai. In *2018 IEEE Conference on Computational Intelligence and Games*
495 *(CIG) (IEEE)*, 1–8
- 496 Tuyen, N. T. V., Jeong, S., and Chong, N. Y. (2018). Emotional bodily expressions for culturally competent
497 robots through long term human-robot interaction. In *2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on*
498 *Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS) (IEEE)*, 2008–2013
- 499 Van de Perre, G., Cao, H.-L., De Beir, A., Esteban, P. G., Lefeber, D., and Vanderborght, B. (2018).
500 Generic method for generating blended gestures and affective functional behaviors for social robots.
501 *Autonomous Robots* 42, 569–580
- 502 Wang, Z., Bapst, V., Heess, N., Mnih, V., Munos, R., Kavukcuoglu, K., et al. (2016). Sample efficient
503 actor-critic with experience replay. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.01224*
- 504 Ye, D., Chen, G., Zhang, W., Chen, S., Yuan, B., Liu, B., et al. (2020). Towards playing full moba games
505 with deep reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2011.12692*
- 506 Zamora, I., Lopez, N. G., Vilches, V. M., and Cordero, A. H. (2016). Extending the openai gym for
507 robotics: a toolkit for reinforcement learning using ros and gazebo. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1608.05742*
- 508 Zhan, Y., Ammar, H. B., and Taylor, M. E. (2017). Scalable lifelong reinforcement learning. *Pattern*
509 *Recognition* 72, 407–418

510 Zhang, A., Ballas, N., and Pineau, J. (2018). A dissection of overfitting and generalization in continuous
511 reinforcement learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.07937*